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CNO in Giant Metal-Poor Stars

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Abstract

We present the chemical abundance analysis for elements carbon, nitrogen, oxygen and the carbon isotopic ratio in a sample of metal-poor stars selected from the RAVE survey based on their extreme radial velocities. Stellar parameters were derived using *Gaia* photometry and parallaxes, and elemental abundances were determined from high-resolution UVES spectra obtained at the ESO Very Large Telescope. The stars span a wide metallicity range ($-2.9 \lesssim [\text{Fe}/\text{H}] \lesssim -1.2$) and, for the majority of the sample, exhibit kinematic properties consistent with the Galactic outer halo population.

1 Introduction

Understanding how the Milky Way formed and evolved requires tracing both its chemical enrichment and its dynamical history. Kinematically hot, metal-poor stars are especially powerful probes in this respect. With their extreme velocities, these stars are associated with the Galactic halo and are thought to preserve signatures of the earliest phases of Galaxy formation.

Because metal-poor stars formed from a gas that has undergone little chemical enrichment, their abundance patterns provide direct insight into early nucleosynthesis. When such low metallicities are combined with extreme kinematics, the stars can also reveal past dynamical events, including accretion of satellite galaxies or strong gravitational interactions. The unprecedented astrometric precision of the *Gaia* mission has transformed this field by enabling reliable kinematic selection of halo stars and efficient follow-up with high-resolution spectroscopy.

Chemical abundance ratios, particularly for elements produced on different timescales, place strong constraints on the assembly history of the Galaxy. Elements such as carbon, nitrogen and oxygen can trace the contributions of stellar populations with different masses and lifetimes.

In this work, I studied a sample of metal-poor stars selected for their high radial velocities. The targets were identified from the RAVE survey and observed with the UVES spectrograph at the ESO Very Large Telescope. The reduced UVES spectra cover the wavelength ranges 328–456 nm and 472–683 nm at a resolving power of $R \sim 40\,000$. To my knowledge, no detailed abundance analysis of these spectra has previously been published.

Table 1: Final Stellar Parameters of the Sample.

Star Name	T_{eff} (K)	$\log g$	ξ (km s^{-1})	[Fe/H]
TYC 7274-00734-1	5032	2.52	1.54	-1.52
TYC 7535-00160-1	4649	1.43	1.96	-2.67
TYC 8019-00159-1	4864	1.72	1.92	-2.51
TYC 7524-00065-1	4503	1.17	1.96	-2.04
C0213360-505024	5486	2.60	1.72	-1.42
C2136142-694908	4561	1.80	1.63	-1.19
C1919566-632839	4069	0.80	0.79	-1.92
C1519196-191359	4319	1.34	1.79	-2.08
C1032508-244851	4970	2.21	1.69	-2.10
C1536201-144228	4888	2.22	1.66	-1.96
C1302091-323721	4223	0.78	1.98	-1.67
C1250398-030748	5443	3.20	1.47	-2.15
C1126364-293415	4196	1.12	1.79	-1.43
C1012254-203007	4520	0.73	2.25	-2.91
C1304064-331913	4189	1.00	1.85	-1.68
C1330590-230955	4000	0.24	2.14	-1.85

2 Stellar parameters and radial velocities

Stellar parameters were derived from *Gaia* EDR3 (Gaia Collaboration et al. 2021) photometry and parallaxes. Reddening corrections were derived using the dust maps of Schlafly & Finkbeiner (2011). Effective temperatures were estimated from the $(G_{\text{BP}} - G_{\text{RP}})$ colour by comparison with theoretical colour– T_{eff} relations from the KOALA database (Mucciarelli et al. 2025). Surface gravities were then computed via the Stefan–Boltzmann relation, using the parallax from *Gaia*. I applied the *Gaia* parallax zero-point correction following Lindegren et al. (2021). Starting from an initial set of atmospheric parameters, metallicities were derived using the MyGIsFOS pipeline (Sbordone et al. 2014). The final parameters are reported in Table 1. With the final stellar parameters, I computed a grid of synthetic spectra for each star, with steps in abundances of 0.2 dex, by using the spectrum synthesis code Turbospectrum (Alvarez & Plez 1998; Plez 2012; Plez et al. 2025), and used these grids to drive the final [O/H] and [Fe/H].

Radial velocities V_r were taken from *Gaia* DR3, where they are obtained from cross-correlation of the RVS spectra. Given the extreme velocities of our targets, I independently verified V_r using the UVES spectra through template matching, adopting the *Gaia* values as initial guesses. The comparison between *Gaia* and UVES-based velocities is summarised in Table 2. Figure 1 places our sample in the broader DR3 radial-velocity distribution, for comparison with the high-velocity population discussed by Katz et al. (2025).

Table 2: Radial velocities from Gaia and this work.

Star Name	V_r^{Gaia} [kms $^{-1}$]	σV_r^{Gaia} [kms $^{-1}$]	V_r^{meas} [kms $^{-1}$]	σV_r^{meas} [kms $^{-1}$]
TYC 7274-00734-1	407.9552	0.2078	408.317	0.4150
TYC 7535-00160-1	355.0691	0.2531	353.523	0.6126
TYC 8019-00159-1	98.4503	0.1710	99.117	0.7179
TYC 7524-00065-1	350.9533	0.2167	351.920	0.4733
C0213360-505024	388.2223	0.6106	388.600	0.7119
C2136142-694908	382.8817	0.3296	381.640	0.4129
C1919566-632839	330.3995	0.5303	328.680	0.5378
C1519196-191359	-409.6939	6.5699	-409.610	0.4705
C1032508-244851	515.3541	2.4702	509.490	0.4929
C1536201-144228	-328.6475	2.1124	-329.600	0.5932
C1302091-323721	409.8165	3.0273	410.000	0.4334
C1250398-030748	396.2207	0.9787	403.020	0.6024
C1126364-293415	409.6741	0.9257	409.870	0.4142
C1012254-203007	508.1379	1.0679	506.755	0.7504
C1304064-331913	357.8247	0.9944	360.720	0.4207
C1330590-230955	334.9188	0.5257	335.350	0.4639

Figure 1: V_r for our sample (pink triangles) compared with the Gaia DR3 radial velocities.

3 Carbon, Nitrogen, Oxygen and Carbon isotopic ratio analysis

For the abundance analysis, I used MyGIsFOS to determine the oxygen abundances. Oxygen was measured using the forbidden [O I] lines at 630.0 nm and 636.3 nm. The derived abundances are presented in Figure 2, where they are compared with the MINCE sample (Cescutti et al. 2022). Oxygen abundances are plotted against Fe II abundances. Our sample (black symbols) is shown alongside metal-poor stars from the MINCE project (red open symbols).

Figure 2: Our sample compared with the sample from Cescutti et al. (2022)

To determine the carbon abundance, I fitted the CH G-band at 430 nm. The molecular data were adopted from Masseron et al. (2014). Nitrogen abundances were derived from the NH band at 336 nm, using the molecular data from Fernando et al. (2018). The spectral regions hosting the G-band and NH band are crowded with atomic lines, requiring careful fitting of the molecular data.

Figure 3 shows the behaviour of carbon and nitrogen abundances as a function of surface gravity. As expected, evolved stars tend to show enhanced nitrogen and depleted carbon. This trend reflects the effects of the internal mixing processes.

Figure 3: Carbon and Nitrogen abundances versus surface gravity.

I was also able to estimate the $^{12}\text{C}/^{13}\text{C}$ ratio. Most of the stars in the sample show low isotopic ratios ($^{12}\text{C}/^{13}\text{C} < 10$), which is a clear signature of internal mixing. These results are consistent with the atmospheric parameters derived for these stars. As shown in Figure 4, the plot indicates that the more evolved stars tend to have $^{12}\text{C}/^{13}\text{C} < 10$, confirming that these stars have undergone mixing.

Figure 4: The relation between Carbon isotopic ratio and surface gravity

We summarise in Table 3 the abundances we derived for oxygen (from the [OI] forbidden lines), carbon (the G-band), nitrogen (the NH band) and the Carbon isotopic ratio.

Lithium

Lithium is detected in two stars of the sample. The Li I line at 670.8 nm in C1012254–203007 is particularly strong. This fact was previously reported by Ruchti et al. (2011) investigating MIKE/Magellan spectra. They derived $A(\text{Li}) = 2.52$ under LTE assumptions, which decreases to $A(\text{Li}) \sim 2.3$ after NLTE corrections. The spectrum here investigated confirms the strength of this line, in agreement with their results. A second star, C1536201–144228, also shows the Li I 670.8 nm feature, although it is weaker. I derived $A(\text{Li}) = 0.82$ in 1D-LTE. I compare in Figure 5 the lithium abundances and carbon isotopic ratios of these stars with the sample of Spite et al. (2006). C1536201–144228 (blue dot in the figure) is perfectly consistent with the comparison sample, while C1012254–203007 has a much larger Li abundance.

Figure 5: Lithium abundances compared with the sample of Spite et al. (2006). Circles represent the Spite et al. (2006) sample and the open circles indicate upper limits. The red point corresponds to C1012254–203007 and the blue one is for the star C1536201–144228.

Table 3: CNO Abundances for the analysed stars.

Star name	T_{eff} (K)	$\log g$	[Fe/H]	A(C)	A(N)	A(O)	12C/13C
TYC7274-00734-1	5032	2.52	-1.52	6.86	6.050	7.81	25
TYC7535-00160-1	4649	1.43	-2.67	5.35	5.778	6.942	8
TYC8019-00159-1	4864	1.72	-2.51	5.28	6.080	no-Oxy	9
TYC7524-0006501	4503	1.17	-2.04	6.04		7.37	5
C0213360-505024	5486	2.60	-1.42	6.59	6.70	7.91	
C2136142-694908	4561	1.80	-1.19	7.07	6.89	8.076	9
C1919566-632839	4069	0.80	-1.92	5.96		7.579	~ 8
C1519196-191359	4319	1.34	-2.08	6.087		7.468	6
C1032508-244851	4970	2.21	-2.10	6.318	5.85	7.244	27
C1536201-144228	4888	2.22	-1.96	6.25		7.58	13
C1302091-323721	4223	0.78	-1.67	6.35		7.732	
C1250398-030748	5443	3.20	-2.15	6.39	5.34	No-Oxy	~ 30
C1126364-293415	4196	1.12	-1.43	6.71		8.066	
C1012254-203007	4520	0.73	-2.91	4.77		6.632	~ 8
C1304064-331913	4189	1.00	-1.68	6.55		7.849	9
C1330590-230955	4000	0.24	-1.85	5.96		7.540	~ 4

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